

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.19387450

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LEADERSHIP SITUATION AND THE ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE IN THE OFFICE OF SPATIAL PLANNING BEKASI CITY, WEST JAVA PROVINCE

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Received: 01/12/2025

Accepted: 02/01/2026

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ABSTRACT

The leadership situation variable (X) is assumed to be related to and influence the organizational climate variable (Y). This research aims to explain whether or not there is and the magnitude of the relationship and influence of the leadership situation on organizational climate. This research was carried out in Bekasi City for 3 (three) months, namely from January to March 2024, taking place at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office. The method (design) used is a survey research method with correlational analysis (in "quantitative analysis"). The population in this study was all employees of the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office, namely 169 people. The number of samples taken was 62 people (30 people from ASN and 32 people from honorary/contract staff). The sampling technique used is engineering proportional random sampling. The data collection method and instrument used was a questionnaire. The data analysis technique is that data collected through questionnaires is analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis techniques and parametric inferential statistics. The results of this research obtained a relationship coefficient (r) of 0.6055. This means that there is a positive relationship between variable X and variable Y (including a strong relationship). The influence or coefficient of determination is (r²) or (0.6055)² = 0.3666. This means that the contribution of the leadership situation to the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office is 36.66%. Related to this, the good leadership situation factor with the support of high-quality leadership needs to be increased to the maximum or even better so that a healthy organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office becomes more conducive. This influence will increase if all employees' commitment is high. This is also in accordance with the view of Islamic law.

KEYWORDS: Quality of Leadership, Healthy Organization, Employee Commitment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Regional offices are implementing agencies of local governments, which may operate at the provincial, regency, or city level. Their functions include formulating technical policies within their scope of authority, issuing permits, providing public services, and supervising the implementation of delegated tasks.

The Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office of West Java Province is one such local government agency. It is led by a head of office under the Mayor of Bekasi through the Regional Secretary. This office carries out decentralized authority based on the principle of regional autonomy and is supported by Technical Implementation Units (UPTDs) responsible for spatial planning tasks across several districts.

The role of regional offices such as this is vital because communities depend on government institutions to deliver services that meet public needs (Etzioni, 2020; Sadler, 2021). In the case of Bekasi, rapid urban growth has created increasingly complex challenges for spatial planning (Mische, 2020). Therefore, the Spatial Planning Office must operate effectively, efficiently, and responsively to ensure alignment with community development needs.

As mandated by Law No. 23 of 2014 on Regional Government, an effective organizational structure is essential. Such a structure is reflected in a healthy organizational climate characterized by flexibility, transparency, motivation, clarity of goals, and personal growth of employees (Riwu Kaho, 2022; Mische, 2020). However, Thoha (2020) and Ancok (2021) observed that many regional government organizations struggle with inefficiency, weak coordination, limited employee competence, and leadership practices that are not adaptive to organizational needs. These issues raise questions about whether the organizational climate in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office is sufficiently conducive.

The organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office has been assessed by several officials as less than conducive. One employee with ASN status noted that many staff members still pay limited attention to work quality, do not fully utilize flexible working hours, and engage in only minimal problem-solving discussions with the head of the office. Similarly, an honorary staff member reported that the head of the office did not fully trust subordinates, gave insufficient attention to the problems they faced, and failed to clearly define all work objectives (Preliminary Survey: Interview results dated March 12 2024)

Whether an organizational climate is conducive depends on multiple factors, one of which is the leadership situation (Fiedler in Gibson *et al.*, 2020; Winardi, 2022). It is assumed that the conduciveness of organizational climate is closely linked to the leader's role, both as an interpersonal actor and as a decision-maker (Thoha, 2020). Creating a positive organizational climate is therefore difficult if leadership is not supportive, particularly in the absence of high-quality leadership. Leaders occupy a central position in directing organizational activities, exercising authority in decision-making, and guiding, mobilizing, and motivating subordinates.

Based on this, the thesis of this article is that the conduciveness of the organizational climate in the context of a healthy organization is significantly related to the quality of leadership. Preliminary observations suggest that the leadership situation at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office has not been optimal, contributing to organizational climate challenges. For example, not all subordinates consistently follow the head's instructions, work procedures are not always clearly explained, and many subordinates perceive the head's performance as unsatisfactory (Preliminary Survey, interview with an echelon IV official, March 17, 2024).

Previous research on leadership situations and their relationship with organizational climate was conducted by Irwansyah (2016) in a study titled "The Influence of Leadership Situations on Organizational Climate in the Mariso District Office, Makassar City, South Sulawesi Province." The study reported a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.8921, indicating a very strong relationship. The coefficient of determination (r^2) was 0.7958, or 79.58%, meaning that nearly four-fifths of the variance in organizational climate could be explained by leadership situations. The research design and variables were similar to the present study, with the main differences being location and timing. Such studies, conducted with consistent methods across different contexts, are valuable for meta-analysis to identify factors that influence the strength of correlation coefficients.

The concept of organizational climate itself refers to the condition of an institution reflected in its working environment. A healthy organizational climate is characterized by flexibility, transparency, motivation, clarity of goals, and opportunities for personal growth among members of the organization (Melcher, 2021). Thus, the indicators of an organizational work climate can be described through several dimensions. First, autonomy and flexibility, which refer to the discretion given to employees to manage their work, including freedom

in utilizing time and resources and recognition of their initiatives by superiors. Second, trust and openness, where leaders demonstrate confidence in their subordinates and provide opportunities for open discussion of various issues. Third, support and empathy, which emphasize the leader's attention to employees' problems, provision of support in accomplishing tasks, and appreciation of employees' contributions to the organization. Fourth, honesty and appreciation, reflecting the importance of integrity in the workplace and the recognition that good performance deserves rewards, with all employees understanding that their individual contributions align with organizational goals. Fifth, clarity of organizational goals, which involves establishing a clear vision, mission, and set of duties so that employees can perform their tasks with focus and direction. Sixth, risk-taking, which highlights employees' confidence in undertaking new responsibilities without fear, including the freedom to constructively disagree with superiors. Finally, personal growth, where employees are encouraged to perform high-quality work and pursue continuous self-development in line with the organization's objectives.

The concept of a leadership situation, as described by Gibson, Ivancevich, and Donnely (2020), refers to the context in which leaders and subordinates interact. This situation has both static and dynamic characteristics, each influencing the stimuli selected by leaders and the quality of subordinate responses (see also Winardi, 2022). According to Fiedler (in Gibson et al., 2020), the leadership situation can be measured through three key dimensions: (1) the leader's relationship with subordinates, (2) the structure of tasks, and (3) the leader's positional power or strength. The conceptual framework of this study is based on the assumption that the leadership situation is significantly related to the organizational climate in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office. In other words, the conduciveness of the organizational climate is partly determined by the quality of leadership. This assumed correlation is illustrated in the following framework.

Figure 1: Framework for Thinking on the Relationship between Leadership Situation and Organizational Climate in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office.

Information:

X: Leadership Situation

AND: Organizational Climate

⇒: relate/influence

The research hypothesis is derived from the conceptual framework and underlying assumptions. This study proposes an associative (symmetric correlation) hypothesis, formulated as follows: "There is a significant relationship between the leadership situation and the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office."

The statistical hypothesis of this research (**which uses a two-party test**) is as follows

To: $\rho = 0$ (meaning there is no relationship/influence).

Ha: $\rho \neq 0$ (meaning there is a relationship/influence; or "not equal to zero" means greater (>) or less (-) than zero, meaning there is a relationship/influence).

ρ = correlation value in the hypothesized formulation (Sugiyono, 2022).

Based on the above discussion, the research problem addressed in this study concerns the relationship between the leadership situation and the organizational climate in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office. Specifically, the research question is: "To what extent does the leadership situation influence the organizational climate in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office?"

2. METHOD

This research was conducted in Bekasi City, specifically at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office. The location was chosen primarily for its accessibility and the relevance of the research object to the study's focus, particularly in addressing the identified problem. Data collection was carried out over a period of three months, from January to March 2024.

The study employed a quantitative survey design with correlational analysis, in which data were collected from a sample of the population to represent the whole. In this design, questionnaires served as the primary data collection instrument. Survey research of this type is commonly used for explanatory purposes, particularly to test correlations and hypotheses (Effendi, 2022).

The conceptual definitions of the study variables are as follows: (1) Organizational climate refers to the condition of an institution reflected in its working environment, characterized by being healthy, effective, and efficient, as well as by demonstrating flexibility, transparency, motivation, clarity of goals, and opportunities for personal growth among its members (Melcher, 2021); and (2) Leadership

situation refers to the context in which leaders and subordinates interact, encompassing both static and dynamic characteristics that influence the stimuli selected by leaders and the quality of subordinate responses (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 2020; Winardi, 2022).

Thus, the operational definitions of the study variables, based on the conceptual definitions above, are as follows

1. Organizational climate refers to the institutional condition of the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office, reflected in a healthy, effective, and efficient working environment characterized by flexibility, transparency, motivation, clarity of organizational and work goals, and opportunities for personal growth among employees. The dimensions measured for this dependent variable are: (i) autonomy and flexibility, (ii) trust and openness, (iii) support and empathy, (iv) honesty and respect, (v) clarity of organizational goals, (vi) risk-taking, and (vii) personal growth. Indicators for these seven dimensions were adapted from established concepts, and measurement was conducted using scores obtained from the organizational climate questionnaire.
2. Leadership situation refers to the context in which the Head of the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office and subordinates interact, characterized by both static and dynamic elements that influence the leader's choices of stimuli and the quality of subordinate responses. The dimensions of this independent variable are: (i) the leader's relationship with subordinates, (ii) task structure, and (iii) positional power or authority of the leader. Indicators for these three dimensions were also derived from prior conceptual frameworks, and measurement was conducted using scores from the leadership situation questionnaire.

The population of this study consisted of all employees of the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office, totaling 169 individuals (124 men and 45 women). The distribution of employees by employment status is presented below.

Table 1: Number of Bekasi City Spatial Planning Service Employees Based on Employee Type (Year 2024)

No.	Type of Officer	Number of people	%
1.	ASN	83	49,7
2.	Honorary/Contract Staff	85	50,3
	Amount	169	100

Source: LKIP Bekasi City Spatial Planning Service, 2024.

Out of 169 employees, 62 respondents were selected through proportional random sampling (30 ASN and 32 honorary staff). According to Arikunto (2023), a sample of more than 30 participants is adequate for correlational studies, especially when representing both subgroups. Furthermore, the sample size exceeds the minimum requirement for achieving sufficient statistical power in Pearson correlation analysis with a medium effect size (Cohen, 1988).

The data for this study were collected using a questionnaire distributed to the 62 respondents selected as the research sample. The instrument was specifically developed to measure the dimensions of the leadership situation and organizational climate.

Both the independent and dependent variables were operationalized through a Likert-scale questionnaire consisting of 38 items: 19 items measuring the leadership situation and 19 items measuring the organizational climate. The questionnaire was designed based on established theoretical dimensions for each variable to ensure comprehensive coverage of the constructs under study. The questionnaire was self-developed based on established concepts of leadership situation (Fiedler in Gibson *et al.*, 2020) and organizational climate (Melcher, 2021). The development of the questionnaire in this study was carried out through several steps. First, indicators and a matrix (grid) for the two variables were established to facilitate control, revision, and consultation with the research supervisor. Second, a set of questions was prepared, each accompanied by scale levels. Third, the draft questionnaire was reviewed in consultation with fellow researchers to ensure clarity and relevance.

The final instrument was designed as a closed-ended questionnaire, in which respondents selected from predefined answer choices. Each item was followed by response options presented in a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). Respondents marked their answers with a check (√) in the corresponding column. All items were formulated positively, avoiding the use of negative phrasing (e.g., "not" or "ignore"). The four-point scale provided gradations from highly positive to highly negative responses, with assigned numerical values serving as comparative measures to facilitate quantification and statistical analysis.

To ensure quality, the instrument underwent expert review (content validity) and a pilot test with 20 respondents outside the main sample. Construct validity was assessed through item-total correlations. Reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha,

which yielded 0.87 for the leadership situation scale and 0.85 for the organizational climate scale, indicating high internal consistency (Nunnally, 1994).

The data collected through questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive and parametric inferential statistical techniques, consistent with the quantitative research design. Descriptive statistics were applied to present frequency distribution tables, histograms, polygons, and percentage calculations. Parametric inferential statistics were then used to calculate measures such as variance and standard deviation.

To test the research hypothesis, Pearson's product-moment correlation was employed to examine the relationship between leadership situation (independent variable) and organizational climate (dependent variable) (Sudjana, 2020). This method was selected to identify both the strength and direction (positive or negative) of the correlation. The significance of the correlation was assessed to determine whether the observed relationship could be generalized to the entire population of 169 employees, from which the 62 respondents were sampled. Significance testing was conducted using critical values from the Pearson r table at a 5% significance level (Sugiyono, 2022). The decision rule was as follows: if $r_{count} < r_{table}$, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, indicating no significant correlation. Conversely, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$, the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, indicating the presence of a significant correlation.

To further strengthen the conclusions, the significance of the correlation coefficient was also tested using a two-tailed t -test. In addition, to predict the extent to which the dependent variable (organizational climate) would change with an increase in the independent variable (leadership situation), a simple regression analysis was performed by calculating the regression equation ($Y = a + bX$).

The analysis was extended by computing the coefficient of determination (r^2), obtained by squaring the correlation coefficient (r). This value indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by variance in the independent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination reflects the extent to which the leadership situation contributes to or influences the organizational climate. This measure is often interpreted as an indication of causal influence (Sugiyono, 2022).

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Islamic University of Jakarta. Informed consent

was obtained from all participants, who were assured of confidentiality and the voluntary nature of their participation. Data were anonymized to protect respondent privacy.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Data Description

First, Leadership Situation Data (Variable X). The instrument used to measure the leadership situation at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office consisted of 19 items, with each item scored on a scale of 1 to 4. Thus, the maximum score per respondent was 76 (4×19), which served as the criterion score. For 62 respondents, the total criterion score was 4,712 (76×62), with an average criterion score of 76. The actual total score obtained for the leadership situation variable was 2,511, which represents 53.29% of the expected score ($2,511 \div 4,712 = 0.5329$). This indicates that the overall leadership situation at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office reached only about half of the ideal (100%).

Although this percentage (53.29%) reflects only the 62 randomly selected respondents from a population of 169 employees, it provides an indication that the leadership situation in the office is present but remains less than optimal. The distribution of scores was quite varied: the highest frequency was found in the interval class of 40–42, with 20 respondents (32.26%), while the lowest frequency occurred in the interval class of 49–51, with only 2 respondents (3.23%).

Second, Organizational Climate Data (Variable Y). The instrument used to measure organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office also consisted of 19 items, each scored on a scale of 1 to 4. Thus, the maximum score per respondent was 76, and for 62 respondents the total criterion score was 4,712.

The actual total score obtained for the organizational climate variable was 2,518, which is equivalent to 53.44% of the expected score ($2,518 \div 4,712 = 0.5344$). This indicates that the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office has reached only about half of the ideal (100%).

Although the percentage (53.44%) reflects only the 62 randomly selected respondents from a population of 169 employees, it provides an indication that a conducive organizational climate has begun to form, but it remains far from optimal. The distribution of scores was quite varied: the highest frequency occurred in the interval class of 39–41, with 18 respondents (29.03%), while the lowest frequencies were found in the first interval class (30–32) and the last interval class (48–50), each with only 2

respondents (3.23%).

From the description above, it can be concluded that there is diversity in the data values for both Variable X (leadership situation) and Variable Y (organizational climate). This variation is reflected in the magnitude of the variance (S^2) and standard deviation (S), while the central tendency of the data is represented by the mean value. A summary of these statistical measures is presented in the following table.

Table 2: Mark Mean, Variance, and Standard Deviation of Variable X and Variable Y.

Variable	Mean	Varians (S^2)	Standard Deviation (S)
X	40,61	19,6182	4,43
AND	50,58	17,9550	4,24

Source: Attachment to the author's calculation results.

To examine the relationship and influence of the leadership situation on the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office, descriptive statistics were first analyzed. For Variable X (leadership situation), the mean score was 40.61. The variable also showed considerable variation, with a standard deviation (S) of 4.43 and a variance (S^2) of 19.6182. The mean and standard deviation represent the central tendency and dispersion of the data, while the variance indicates the degree of variation in individual responses within the sample.

Similarly, for Variable Y (organizational climate), the mean score was 50.58, which falls within the medium range. This variable also demonstrated variability, with a standard deviation (S) of 4.24 and a variance (S^2) of 17.9550. These values suggest that the organizational climate scores ranged approximately from 46.34 ($50.58 - 4.24$) to 54.82 ($50.58 + 4.24$).

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that improvements in the leadership situation are likely to contribute to better organizational climate outcomes at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office, although additional efforts are also required to achieve optimal conditions.

3.2. Statistical Hypothesis Test Results

First, the statistical hypothesis that will be tested in this research using a two-party test is as follows: if $H_0 : \rho = 0$, then it means there is no positive and significant relationship or influence between the leadership situation and the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office. Meanwhile, if $H_a : \rho \neq 0$, then it means there is a positive and significant relationship and/or influence between the leadership situation and the organizational

climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office, or if it is "not equal to zero", meaning it is greater ($>$) or less ($-$) than zero, meaning there is a relationship or influence, where ρ = the value of the relationship or influence in the hypothesized formulation.

The correlation formula (relationship) used to test the statistical hypothesis mentioned above is the correlation formula product moment from Pearson. From the calculation results, the relationship coefficient (r) is 0.6055. This means that there is a positive relationship between variable X and variable Y (including a strong relationship).

There are 3 (three) forms of variable relationships (two or more variables) that can occur in a study, **namely** (1) positive relationship, (2) negative relationship, and (3) no relationship, **as described below**

Source: Marvian (2022).

Figure 2: Forms of Variable Relationships (Two or More Variables).

If an increase in one variable X is followed by an increase in another variable (Y), then it can be said that the two variables have a positive relationship. But on the contrary, if an increase in one variable is followed by a decrease in another variable, then it can be said that the two variables have a negative relationship. If there are no changes in one variable even in another variable, then the two variables have no relationship. The results of this research include a positive relationship (the first form of relationship in the picture above), meaning that an increase in variable X (leadership situation) is followed by an increase in variable Y (organizational climate).

Second, to predict how high variable Y will be if variable X is increased, a simple regression technique is used, by calculating a simple regression line equation. The simple regression line equation formula is as follows: $Y = a + bX$, where Y = Variable Y (dependent variable); a = Regression constant; b = Regression coefficient; and X = Variable X (independent variable).

From the calculation results, the regression line equation is obtained ($Y = a + bX$), namely: $Y = 16.895 + 0.59 X$. The intersection of each axis is as follows: Y = 16.895 + 0.59 X; intersection with the X axis, then $Y = 0$. So $0 = 16.895 + 0.59 - 0.59 X = 16.895$; $X = -16.895$:

0.59 = - 28.6356. Thus, the coordinates are (-28.6356 ; 0). Intersect with the Y axis, then X = 0. Y = 16.895 + 0.59 (0) = 16.895. The coordinates are (0 ; 16.895). If the equation is drawn, **it will look like below**

Figure 3: Organizational Climate Regression Lines Due to Correlation with the Leadership Situation in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office.

Based on the picture above, the ups and downs or levels of conducive organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office can be predicted using the regression line equation. The question then is, if the level of good leadership situation is increased to the maximum, how much will the conducive organizational climate increase in the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office occur?

Based on the data on variable the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office is: $Y = 16.895 + 0.59 (X)$; $Y = 16.895 + 0.59 (76)$, which means that $Y = 16.895 + 44.84 = 61.735$. It turns out that if the level of goodness of the leadership situation is increased to a maximum of 76, the level of conduciveness of the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Service Office increases or increases from 44.84 to 61.735. However, it should be noted that even though

Third, to test the significance of the relationship above, namely whether the relationship found applies to the entire population of 169 people, it is necessary to test its significance. The significance tests used are practical significance tests and significance tests using the t test. The practical significance test does not need to be calculated using a formula, but directly consulted in the r table product moment. As for the critical price from table r product moment, with a significance level of $p = 0.05$ (5%) and $N = 62$, r is obtained table of 0.254 (see List of Critical Price Tables "r" Product Moment). Thus $r_{count} > r_{table}$ ($0.6055 > 0.254$). This means that there

is a significant relationship between variable X and variable Y.

To strengthen the conclusions above, it is also necessary to test the significance of the correlation coefficient or relationship or test the hypothesis using a two-party test via the t test. From the calculation results, $t = 5.8844$. Price tcount This is then compared with the price ttable Frequency Distribution Values t with α for two-tailed test (two tail-test) (see attached Table). For a 5% error in a two-tailed test and $dk = n$ or $62 - 2 = 60$, then we get $t_{table} = 2,000$. **This can be described as follows**

Figure 4: Test the Significance of the Correlation Coefficient Using a Two-Party Test.

So, H_0 is rejected, because $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($5.8844 > 2.000$). Alternatively, it can be stated that t_{count} (5.8844) falls in the H_0 rejection region, which means H_0 (hypothesis null) which states there is no relationship between the leadership situation and organizational climate is rejected, and H_a (alternative hypothesis) is accepted (there is a relationship). This means that the results are the same as the previous practical significance test which was not calculated using a formula such as the t test above, which means that there is a significant relationship between variable X and variable Y, where the coefficient can be generalized or can apply to the population from which the sample of 169 people was taken.

Fourth, Based on the previous calculation, the correlation coefficient (r) was 0.6055, resulting in a coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.3666 (0.6055^2). This indicates that 36.66% of the variation in organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office can be explained by the leadership situation. In other words, the conduciveness of the organizational climate is partly determined by the quality of leadership, and this influence would likely increase if employee commitment were stronger.

The contribution of the leadership situation is particularly important because it helps shape an organizational climate characterized by trust, which in turn influences perceptions, actions, and communication within the organization (Nufus, 2021). A conducive organizational climate has been shown to positively and significantly affect employee performance (Khairaningsih & Sobirin, 2022; Guna et

al., 2022) and serves as an organizational characteristic that distinguishes one institution from another (Hasbi *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, a supportive climate can enhance the effectiveness of employee services (Rahmisyari, 2020), provided that it is reinforced by favorable ecological conditions (Utami *et al.*, 2021). In this context, external environmental factors, organizational strategy, structure, historical dynamics, and continuous improvements in leadership all interact to form a system that sustains a conducive organizational climate.

Leadership plays a crucial role in driving organizational activities (Sahadi *et al.*, 2020) and is therefore one of the most important determinants of organizational success. Strong leadership is essential for achieving organizational goals (Setiani *et al.*, 2023). However, building effective leadership relationships within an organization is not an easy task (Utari & Hadi, 2020), as each organizational line carries its own consequences, shaped by both formal and informal ideological constructions among the actors involved.

Supportive leadership has been shown to positively and significantly influence human resource productivity, particularly through fostering positive employee perceptions (Fajar *et al.*, 2022). Leadership also plays a vital role in enhancing the quality of public services (Syahabuddin *et al.*, 2021). In this regard, an effective leadership situation requires strong leadership capacity, harmonious superior-subordinate relationships, the commitment and support of all employees, and a consistent orientation toward delivering satisfactory public services.

Fifth, research results and relationship to the Islamic legal perspective. The results of this study show a positive and significant relationship between the leadership situation and the organizational climate at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office. The correlation coefficient of 0.6055 indicates that better leadership is associated with a more conducive organizational climate. From an Islamic legal perspective, this finding aligns with the principle that leadership is an *amanah* (trust and responsibility) that must be exercised with justice and exemplary conduct. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) emphasized that every leader will be held accountable for their decisions, making good leadership a key factor in creating a harmonious work environment (Ali, 2015).

Justice within organizations is also a fundamental principle in Islam. This study found that 36.66% of the variation in organizational climate is explained by leadership, which corresponds to Allah's

command in the Qur'an to act justly. Injustice in the distribution of tasks or rewards can harm morale, whereas fairness fosters a positive climate (QS. An-Nahl: 90). The Prophet further reminded that leaders who ignore the needs of their people or subordinates will face equivalent consequences before Allah (Hasrawi *et al.*, 2019).

Moreover, this study highlights the relevance of servant leadership in improving organizational climate. The regression equation ($Y = 16.895 + 0.59X$) demonstrates that strengthening leadership quality positively impacts the work environment. In Islam, the ideal leader is characterized by humility and concern for subordinates, as exemplified by the Prophet Muhammad. When leaders in government institutions such as the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office adopt these principles listening to employees' aspirations, offering support, and demonstrating empathy the organizational climate becomes more conducive (Wahbah az-Zuhaili, 2016).

The significance test ($t_{count} = 5.8844 > t_{table} = 2.000$) confirms that the relationship between leadership and organizational climate did not occur by chance. From the perspective of Islamic law, this highlights the importance of self-evaluation (*muhasabah*) for leaders. Allah SWT commands believers to engage in continuous introspection to avoid error (QS. Al-Hasyr: 18). In practice, when leaders in government agencies regularly evaluate policies and their interactions with staff, the organizational climate can be continuously improved (Shihab, 2002).

Nevertheless, this study also indicates that stronger leadership alone does not guarantee an optimal organizational climate. Other factors, such as communication, reward and punishment systems, and organizational culture, also play influential roles. Islam offers solutions through the reinforcement of sharia-based values within organizations, including transparency, deliberation (*shura*), and honesty. Applying these principles enables government institutions to foster a more positive work environment and deliver more effective public services.

In conclusion, the findings of this study reinforce the importance of leadership grounded in Islamic values for building a conducive organizational climate. By implementing principles of justice, accountability, and servant leadership, government agencies can enhance organizational productivity and performance. Thus, institutions such as the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office may consider adopting a sharia-based approach in leadership and organizational management to achieve better

outcomes.

4. CONCLUSION

The conduciveness of the organizational climate has a positive and significant relationship with the quality of leadership. This study at the Bekasi City Spatial Planning Office demonstrates that the organizational climate is strongly influenced by the leadership situation. Accordingly, leadership must be strengthened not only by the head of the office but

also by all structural officials under their authority. Improving the leadership situation requires, among other things, building harmonious relationships between leaders and subordinates, ensuring that all tasks are clearly explained by the head of the office, and exercising authority in ways that support the achievement of the office's vision and mission. These findings are also consistent with the principles of Islamic law, which emphasize justice, accountability, and responsibility in leadership.

Acknowledgements: The author would like to thank Universitas Islam Jakarta and the National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN) Jakarta for their support in compiling the results of this research.

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